

Power Oscillation Damping Capabilities of Grid Forming Based Hybrid Energy Storage Technology

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Abstract— This paper presents the power oscillation damping (POD) capabilities of a Hybrid Energy Storage System (HES) based on ultracapacitors (UCAP) and batteries, integrated with a Grid-Forming (GFM) conversion system. The proposed system is designed to address challenges associated with low-inertia power grids, providing enhanced damping through both internal (inherent) and external POD control mechanisms. Adapting to the latest requirements set by the Spanish system operator (REE), this study highlights how the HES-GFM solution effectively mitigates power oscillations while maintaining grid stability under dynamic conditions. By emulating synchronous generator behavior and leveraging hybridization at the DC side of the GFM converter, the system demonstrates superior performance in delivering POD services compared to conventional systems. The proposed activation algorithm for POD, compared to conventional systems, ensures reduced stress on the storage components, thereby extending battery life. This highlights the crucial role of advanced hybrid storage technologies and smart control strategies in enhancing grid stability, meeting evolving grid codes, and supporting a sustainable energy transition. The activation logic recommended by the system operator emerges as the key differentiator from conventional POD approaches.

Keywords—*Hybrid energy storage, Energy integration, Grid forming converter, Low inertia systems, Power Oscillation Damping, Power System Control.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) into modern power grids has introduced significant challenges to maintaining system stability. Among these challenges, reduced system inertia due to the replacement of synchronous generators with inverter-based resources has become a critical concern for grid operators [1]-[2].

The transition toward low-inertia grids, driven by decarbonization goals, has heightened the need for advanced technologies that can mimic the inertia and stability services traditionally provided by conventional generation [3]-[4]. The adoption of renewable energy technologies such as solar and wind power has surged significantly. These renewable sources are typically integrated into the grid through power electronic converters, predominantly utilizing Grid Following (GFL) control. GFL converters synchronize their output with the grid's frequency and voltage to facilitate power injection but lack the capability to provide inherent inertia or stability services. Unlike synchronous generators, these converters do not contribute to grid inertia, a critical component for maintaining stability during transient disturbances such as load changes or faults. This limitation has prompted the development and adoption of Grid Forming (GFM) converters. GFM converters autonomously establish and control grid voltage and frequency, effectively emulating the behavior of synchronous machines and providing essential stability services such as virtual inertia or inherent damping and Power oscillation damping (POD) to modern grids [3]-[7].

POD has become a critical service to address the issue of electromechanical oscillations and stability challenges in low-inertia systems. Electromechanical oscillations, often triggered by events such as line faults or generator trips, pose significant risks to system reliability, particularly in grids with diminished natural damping [8]-[9]. Effective POD strategies are essential for mitigating these oscillations and preventing cascading failures. Recognizing the importance of this issue, many European system operators have revised their grid codes to address the challenges posed by high renewable penetration and low inertia. For example, the Spanish grid operator, Red Eléctrica de España (REE) has introduced comprehensive guidelines to ensure the integration of POD functionalities within low-inertia systems, reflecting the growing need for robust and adaptive solutions to support renewable energy integration [10].

Electromechanical oscillations are typically categorized into local oscillations, occurring between nearby coherent generator groups with frequencies ranging from 0.7 to 2.5 Hz, and inter-area oscillations, which occur between distant generator groups with frequencies around 0.1 to 1 Hz. Historically, small-signal stability was largely influenced by the dynamics of synchronous machines. However, in today's power systems, dominated by power electronic converters, these devices significantly affect stability phenomena, giving rise to what is now referred to as converter-driven stability. The importance of addressing low-inertia challenges has been increasingly recognized by transmission system operators (TSOs) across Europe. This leads to implementing more pilot projects at the national level to test such supplementary services. As an example, a pilot project with POD controllers for a grid following based system for a wind power park application with energy storage system has been carried out recently in Spain [11].

Traditionally, synchronous machines utilize Power System Stabilizers (PSS) to enhance damping, whereas facilities relying on power-electronic-based technologies, such as Power Park Modules (PPM), Energy Storage Systems (ESS), incorporate Power Oscillation Damping (POD) controllers. While the application of POD controllers has been extensively studied for

Voltage Source Converters (VSC) with Grid-Following (GFL) control in systems like wind and solar PPMs, energy storage systems, and HVDC setups [12]-[14], recent advancements have introduced POD controllers for VSCs with Grid-Forming (GFM) capabilities [15]. These developments underscore the evolving role of POD control strategies in addressing stability challenges within modern grids. Virtual synchronous machines with inherent damping capabilities have garnered attention for their ability to enhance system dynamics. Unlike GFL converters, which follow the grid, GFM converters actively contribute to grid stability by emulating key properties of synchronous machines, such as inertia and damping, making them indispensable for low-inertia systems.

Despite the promise of GFM controls, practical implementation often requires additional capabilities to meet the diverse operational demands of modern grids. Auxiliary energy storage systems, particularly those connected to the DC side of GFM converters, play a key role in extending the functionality of these systems on providing various services to the grid. Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS), which combine ultracapacitors (UCAPs) and batteries, have emerged as a robust solution for addressing these demands. By leveraging the complementary strengths of UCAPs and batteries, HESS can provide both fast-acting power support and long-duration energy services, enhancing the overall performance of GFM systems [16].

HESS offers several advantages over traditional single-technology storage systems. UCAPs deliver high power density and rapid response, making them ideal for addressing transient events and power smoothing. Meanwhile, batteries provide energy-based services such as frequency regulation and peak shaving. This hybrid approach eliminates the need to oversize battery systems, reducing both capital and operational costs while minimizing degradation. As a result, HESS enables GFM converters to deliver a wider range of ancillary services, including such as virtual inertia, and oscillation damping.

This study focuses on the power oscillation damping capabilities of a novel HESS-GFM system, which has been designed in accordance with the latest requirements of the Spanish system operator, Red Eléctrica de España (REE). By integrating advanced control strategies at both internal and external levels, the proposed system is capable of mitigating power oscillations effectively while enhancing overall grid stability. The key contributions of this paper are:

- Analysis of the control architecture of the HESS-GFM system, showcasing its capability on transition from island to grid connected mode while providing inherent local damping as well as external POD for interconnected power systems.
- An exploration of the benefits of hybrid energy storage systems (HESS) that combine ultracapacitors (UCAPs) for high-power applications and batteries for high-energy responses, presenting an optimized hybrid solution for grid stability and operational efficiency.
- A detailed investigation of the latest recommendations from Red Eléctrica de España (REE) regarding the integration of POD controllers, including the effects of the PODp enabler mechanism, ensuring accurate and effective activation of POD functionalities.

The findings presented in this paper underscore the importance of deploying advanced hybrid energy storage technologies to ensure grid stability and meet evolving operational demands in low-inertia systems. By addressing both theoretical and practical aspects, this study aims to provide valuable insights for researchers, and grid operators to enhance the stability and reliability of future modern grid.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the studied system, introducing the two power system configurations used to validate the proposed hybrid energy storage system (HESS) with grid-forming (GFM) control. Section III details the control structure and its hierarchical organization, highlighting the roles of each control layer. Section IV is dedicated to the simulation results, demonstrating the performance of the proposed control strategy under various operating scenarios. Finally, Section V concludes the paper with a summary of the key findings.

II. STUDIED SYSTEM

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the grid forming control and hybrid solution (HESS), two different test systems are considered. The first test system is shown in Fig. 1 is presenting a full HESS system with a Wind park which can work in island thanks to GFM capabilities. This test system is used to show the inherent damping capabilities of the proposed GFM based HESS system. For further demonstration of external damping capabilities of POD controller according to the last recommendation of Spanish TSO (REE) a second testing scenario shown in Fig. 2 is used [10]. This testing system is consists of two areas, loads and four synchronous generators, modified two area Kundur model [17]. The full HESS system is connected to bus number 2. The rating and generic technical data of both systems can be found in Table 1 and 2.

TABLE 1. SYSTEM DATA1.

External grid equivalent	Ex. Loads	Local Load	Cable (Lg)
Rating: 100 MVA 12 kV, Inertia: 3 s	P= 30 MW Q= 6MVAR	P=1.62 MW Q=0 MVAR	Length: 0,5 km R = 0,125 Ω /km, X _l = 0,106 Ω /km C = 0,306 μ F/km

TABLE 2. SYSTEM DATA2.

Synchronous Generators	Ex. Loads	Transformers	Lines
SG1:1500MVA, H= 6.3s @20kV	L1 @BUS6: P:1250 MW,	T1,6: 1500MVA,	R: 1e-7 pu,

Synchronous Generators	Ex. Loads	Transformers	Lines
	@ 400 kV	19 kV / 400 kV	XL:0.65 pu,
SG4:5000MW, H=6.17s@20kV	L2 @BUS9: P: 4000 MW, @ 400kV	T9,3:5000 kVA, 400 kV/19 kV T2,14:1500kVA 400kV/132 kV	B: 0 (100 MW base)

As illustrated in both test systems, a grid forming HESS system is integrated and validated for providing different services. The designed HESS conversion system consists of a battery with a peak power rating of 8 MW, an energy capacity of 3.494 MWh, and a nominal voltage of 1.15 kV. Additionally, it includes an ultracapacitor (UCAP) rated at approximately 18 MW peak power, with a total capacitance of 170.4 F and a voltage range between 0.97 kV and 1.44 kV. In this HESS system two energy management systems referred to as InMS are utilized. The InMS® (Intelligent Node Management System), functioning as an EMS, is a combined hardware and software platform designed to incorporate advanced algorithms for optimal planning and multi-service operation by end users. This system is tailored to achieve efficient energy management based on a thorough understanding of storage technologies and their behavior in real-world, grid-scale applications.

In this study, two variants of InMS control are implemented. The first, known as InMS-SHAD, is responsible for controlling and parameterizing the power electronics associated with the HESS system, ensuring rapid-response services by leveraging fast signal acquisition from the DC bus. The second, InMS-uGRID, operates at a higher level, managing microgrid operations, SCADA supervision, and interfacing with other electrical assets.

Figure 1. Test system 1: HESS system connected to an equivalent grid.

III. HIERARCHICAL CONTROL STRUCTURE

The hierarchical control framework for managing various control levels in grid-forming (GFM) power electronic-based generation units is illustrated in Fig. 3. An Intelligent Node Management System has been developed to implement flexible, advanced control strategies and to validate the capabilities of the HESS GFM system. Communication will be facilitated using Modbus over TCP, which serves as the standard protocol for enabling the InMS to interface with other devices and systems effectively.

As depicted in Fig. 3, the primary control layer (CTRL1) includes the inner current controller at the power electronics level, responsible for generating the modulated voltage signals for the converter. The second control level (CTRL2) is mainly related

Figure 2. Test system 2: Modified two-area system with integrated HESS system at BUS 14.

to the outer loop controllers and grid functionalities, which is giving proper input signal to CTRL1. Additional grid functionalities can be utilized as part of CTRL2 and CTRL3 outer loop controls such as Virtual inertia and Frequency control or POD. Fig. 4 illustrates the core grid-forming functionality, situated at the CTRL2 level, where voltage and angle control are performed. In this study, the DC side is shared between the battery and UCAP, allowing the UCAP to handle fast response actions while the battery manages the remaining demands. Combining these two technologies into a hybrid system enables the provision of diverse services such as virtual inertia, power oscillation damping (POD). The third and fourth control levels (CTRL3 and CTRL4) focus on supplementary tasks, component coordination, and virtualization. Fig. 3, presents control sections for providing virtual angle of a synchronous machine control emulating the inertial response and the reactive power/voltage control for providing the voltage amplitude to the grid forming system.

The high-level control incorporates a self-synchronization mechanism that enables the converter to operate in harmony with an external grid. Various types of self-synchronization methods exist, including power-frequency (P-f) droop control and virtual synchronous machine (VSM) control [4]. This mechanism provide a reference angle, which is then fed as an input to the CTRL2 level. The hierachy of the designed external POD control structure is shown in Fig. 5. According to the last recommendation from REE, PODq will be always active but PODp will be activated if the amplitude of oscillation reach a defined threshold.

As shown in Fig. 5, since PODp is linked to P-channel the during its activation it will be coordinated with APC and SOC controllers. The output of the POD controller will provide a transient setpoint (ΔP_{cons} or ΔQ_{cons}) added to the main setpoints. Since electromechanical oscillations are well observed at the frequency of the different nodes of the system, different options can be used for observing the frequency at the connection point to detect system oscillations. In this case, a general scheme of the POD-P control of an ESS with enabler signal is presented. The POD-P control will be activated only in case of detection of a sustained amplitude in time seen at the connection point frequency, whose amplitude is greater than or equal to a specified threshold (f_{th}).

Figure 3. Control structure of the GFM power converter-based unit.

Figure 4. Outer control loop at the CTRL2 level.

Figure 5. Hierarchical structure of POD in both P and Q-channel of control at the plant level control.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the developed GFM control concept is tested with the equivalent grid shown in Fig. 1. The used data for this test are presented in Table 1. While for having a better contribution to the SCR of the used small system, a smaller virtual admittance has been selected. The goal of this test is to check the following capabilities:

- Operation of the converter in transition from Island to grid connected mode with inherent damping capabilities of GFM HESS converter system.
- External POD capability of the proposed solution using the second test system.

The simulation is managed to have the initialization part in PSCAD and then checking the starting up the HESS converter in island mode. The used wind power profiles for this scenario are shown in Figs 6.

The converter was able to automatically increase its output power for feeding the local loads and getting synchronized around 16.5 sec. After switching to grid connected mode, the converter is changing its active power output as the power setpoint requested for grid connected mode operation while during island mode operation it was only feeding the local loads.

The results of the damping on both active and reactive power signals at the output of the GFM converter system are presented in Fig. 7 and 8.

Figure 6. Active and reactive power curves of Wind Park.

The obtained results and proof clearly the capability of the proposed GFM system on forming the grid and transition from island to grid connected mode at 16.5 sec while at the same time it demonstrates the damping capabilities of the local signals by changing their corresponding damping values of the GFM controller itself.

Figure 7. Local active power damping capability of HESS system

Figure 8. Local reactive power damping capability of HESS system

Results shown in Fig. 7 and 8 for different damping values of 30, 50 and 120 in PLC block with frequency of oscillation of 4 Hz, 5 Hz and 6 Hz are compared. It shows higher damping gain is resulting less oscillation on the signal. For the second test, the proposed two-area test system shown in Fig. 2 is used for assessing the capability of external POD control for damping the oscillations of the used grid.

The used control parameters for this test is presented in Tables 3 and 4. In this test, after normal operation in grid-connection, a load step change after 10 sec at BUS 9 leading to oscillation in two-area system.

Table 31. PODp global parameters

PODp parameters	value
Frequency sensitivity (activation)	15 mHz
POD-P proportional gain (Kpod-p)	400 pu
Washout filter (Tw)	7 s
Filter time constant (Tp)	0.1 s
Power saturation limits	20 MVA
Droop gain of LPC	1 pu

Table 4. PODq global parameters

PODp parameters	value
POD-q proportional gain (Kpod-q)	150 pu
Washout filter (Tw)	7 s
Filter constant (Tq)	0.1 s
Power saturation limits	20 MVA
Droop gain of RPC	1 pu

The angular difference between the two generators of two area test system comparing different controls are presented in Fig. 9. As it can be observed the outcome of PODpq is providing the highest damping. The simulations demonstrate the algorithm's capacity to rapidly identify and suppress power oscillations, maintaining system stability even under severe conditions. In order to see the effects of activation block for POD using a detailed activation algorithm proposal, specific results are compared in Fig. 10 to 12. As can be seen, after almost 25 sec the proposed POD is deactivated with successful operation of signal damping.

Figure 9. Frequency difference between the two generators with and without POD controllers and activation algorithm.

In fig. 11, the stream of different modes for frequency base of 0.1 Hz and 0.5 Hz for different stream of oscillatory harmonics are presented. It has been designed in a way that the activation algorithm block can cover a range of oscillation from 0.1 to 3.5 Hz. Therefore, it makes it possible to have full monitoring of different modes, assessing their amplitude and activate the POD if the amplitude of each mode is higher than a threshold of 0.015 Hz. The power at the POI and output power of HESS due to activation and deactivations of POD, following the activation block order, is presented in Figs 11 to 13.

Figure 10. Frequency of generators of interconnected test system2 (Left: No POD, Right: with PODpq activation algorithm).

It shows that the proposed POD will be activated only when it is really needed, based on the monitored modes of oscillation within the range of interest. During certain periods, the POD is disabled, and even after 25 seconds, it is fully deactivated because the amplitude of the modes is below the threshold. This has a great advantage in reducing stress and cycling on the battery for long-term operation.

Figure 11. Activation signal analysis, amplitude of different modes; Left: base frequency of 0.1 Hz, Right: base frequency of 0.5 Hz.

Figure 12. Power at the POI for PODpq with activation algorithm effect; Left: P(MW), Right Q[MVar].

Figure 13. Storage power outputs [MW] with POD with activation algorithm effect; Left: BESS output, Right: UCAP output.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the effectiveness of a Grid Forming (GFM) hybrid energy storage system in addressing the stability challenges of low-inertia power grids. Through a detailed PSCAD simulations, the proposed GFM-HESS architecture demonstrated its capability to operate seamlessly in both grid-connected and islanded modes, with automatic switching between these states. The integration of batteries and ultracapacitors (UCAPs) offers a robust solution for enhancing dynamic stability, as UCAPs alleviate stress on the batteries during short-term, high-power demands, thereby improving system performance and longevity. Moreover, an updated POD controller design and testing framework, aligned with the latest recommendations from Red Eléctrica de España (REE), was introduced. This includes an accurate activation mechanism for POD functionalities, such as the activation block for PODp, ensuring precise and efficient damping of power oscillations with less stress over batteries especially compared to conventional method. These findings underline the potential of hybridization to provide advanced ancillary services, offering a pathway to achieve stable and resilient grids with high renewable energy penetration.

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